

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MENTAL HEALTH PROFILES IN HEALTHY-WEIGHT VS. OBESE WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was investigated to mental health among Normal and obesity women. The random sampling Method was used in this study. The total sample consisted 60 women. 30 of normal and 30 of obesity women from Bhanvnagar city. Along with the respective personal data sheet and Mental Health scale developed by Dr. Jagdish & Dr. A.K.shrivastav used from date collection. Data was analyzed by 't' test verify the hypothesis. The result shows that 't' value is 3.6 that is significant at 0.01 level. So, the hypothesis is not accepted. It means normal and obesity women was very far difference between mental Health.

Key words: Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

Conceptualization of Health as "A State of complete physical, mental and social well- being and not merely absence of disease or inferiority." By the World Health Organization in its 1946 charter has gone a long way in changing the focus of health professionals.

Mental health is a balance between all aspect of life - social physical, spiritual and emotional aspect of a person. It imparts on how we manage our surroundings and make choices in our lives- clearly it is an integral part of our overall health (Negi, 2010)

The world population is becoming rounder, and each year the situation is worsening, the world Health Organization (WHO) believes that we are in the grip of a global epidemic, and it is estimated by the year 2020 obesity will be the single biggest killer on the planet.

Professor Philip James, Chairman of the International obesity Task force, said that "We now know that the biggest global health Burden for the world is dietary in origin and is compounded by association with low Physical activity levels. This is going to plague as for the next 30 year."

Currently at least 300 million adults world wide are obese a body mass index (BMI) of over 30 and over one billion are overweight (BMI of More that 27.3 percent for women and 27.8 percent or more for men) the problems affects virtually all ages and socioeconomic groups.

One of the important goals of health psychology is to help people attain and maintain a healthy weight, not necessarily the cultural ideal. to this end psychologists have joined forces with molecular biologists, genetic engineers, nutritionists and other health professionals in the search for answers to some of eating behavior's most puzzling questions. Why is obesity becoming more prevalent, not only in developed country but also developing country throughout the world ?How is it that some people can eat whatever they want without gaining, weight, whole others remains overweight despite constant dieting? To get answer all the eating behavior and weight regulation by examining the components of foods and their role in maintaining health.

Mental Health refers to the development, preservation, prevention and treatment and enhancement of total personality in all its varied aspects.

2. "HEALTH IS WEALTH"

Obesity may be defined as an abnormal growth of the adipose tissues due to an enlargement of fat cell size (hypertrophic obesity) or an increase in fat cell number (hyperplastic obesity) or a combination of both. Obesity is often expressed in terms of body mass index (BMI) BMI is one of the objective and prominent determinant of health of an individual. The term "overweight" means a weight in excess of the average for a given sex, height and age.

Although being slightly overweight appears to pose no health risks, obesity presents a major risk.

A variety of treatment approaches to obesity exist. These include diet counseling, diet modification, behavior modification, exercise, pharmacotherapy surgery, commercial or self - help programs and school - based programs

Compared to adults with normal weight, adults with a BMI greater than 30 are more likely to be diagnosed with coronary heart disease (CHD) hyper tension, stroke, high cholesterol, goar, osteoarthritis, sleep problems., asthma, skin condition and some types of cancer.

Psychological disorders which obesity may trigger include depression, eating, disorders, distorted body image and low self esteem.

3. RELATED STUDY

Katz, D.A.et al" Impact of Obesity on Health related quality of Life in Patients with chronic illness"
Journal of General Internal Medicine. Vol. 15 November 2000, PP 789- 96

4. OBJECTIVE

- To compare Mental Health of normal and obesity womens.

5. HYPOTHESIS

- There is no significant difference between normal and obesity womens in mental health.

6. VARIABLE

(i) Independent Variable

- Normal women, Obesity women.

(ii) Depended Variable:-

- To get score on mental health among normal & obesity women.

7. SAMPLE

The sample consisted of 60 (30 normal women and 30 obesity women) the sample was selected by random method from BHANAVNAGAR City.

8. TOOLS

In this research mental health questionnaire where used from the data collection contracted and standardize by or Dr. Jagdish and Dr. A.K. Shrivastav. The reliability is 0.73 and the validity is 0.54.

9. STATISTICAL METHOD

Hear in this study "t" test was used for data interpretation.

RESULT TABLE

Variable	Sample (N)	Mean	SED	't' value	level of significance
Normal women	30	156.27	3.3	3.6	0.01
Obesity women	30	144.4			

Significance = 0.01 = 2.66

10. RESULT DICISTION

The outcome of the present study clearly indicates that there is a lot's of difference between the Normal women and obesity women in terms of mental health. The mean of Normal women are 156.27 and obesity women are 144.4. It is clear that mental health level of obesity women is less as compared to Normal women. The highest mean of mental Health is of the Normal women and lowest mean of mental Health is of the obesity women. Results show that difference in m mental health of obesity women and normal womens.

According to the 't' test the numeric value that we get is 3.6 which is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in mental health among normal and obesity women is not acceptable. It means Normal women and Obesity women was very far difference between Mental Health

11. CONCLUSION

There is significant difference in Mental Health among Normal and Obesity women. (t= 3.6)

REFERENCES

1. Amrita Yadava and Nov Rattan Sharma, "*Positive Health Psychology*", First Edition, 2007, global vision publishing House , 20 Ansari Road, Daryayanj, New Delhi - 110 002 (India)
2. Jeri freedman, "The mental and physical Effects of obesity" The Rosen Publishing group 2008 - Juvenile nonfiction -64 page (2008)
3. Katz, D.A.Etal" Impact of obesity on Health – "Related quality of life in patients with chronic illness", *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, Vol. 15 November 2000, pp 789 - 96
4. Roberts, R.E. et. al. Prospective association between obesity and depression: evidence from the alamed county study, *International Journal of obesity and related metabolic Disorders*, Vol. 27, April, 2003. pp 514- 21.
5. Written by Jane Colling Wood, 'Obesity and Mental health" May 21, 2007 at 5.38 PM. <http://thinforlife.med.nyu.edal/.obesity>.